

A 2014 update on special glasses for use at work in Norway

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Abstract

On a more or less a biannual basis, for almost ten years, The Norwegian Association of Optometry has performed market surveys in Norway. Typically, slightly more than 1000 randomly selected Norwegians, at the age of 15 years and above, have constituted the study participants. They were all contacted by professional telephone interviewers. Among the questions addressed were also the questions listed below:

- Do you have special glasses for use at work?
- Do you feel a need of a special pair of glasses for use at work?
- Have there been measurements at your work place for your special work glasses? • Are the costs for an eye examination partly or fully covered by your employer?
- Are the costs of a pair of special work glasses partly or fully covered by your employer?

A new survey is planned for the spring of 2014, and the results will be presented and discussed in the oral presentation. The results for the previous four surveys are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Percentage of people having special glasses for use at work in Norway 2005-2012.

This presentation will focus on the numbers of special glasses for the use at work revealed in the survey performed in 2014. It is speculated that most people giving a positive answer at the question on “special glasses”, actually use special glasses for computer work. The presentation will further include a discussion comparing the numbers for Norway; with numbers for other countries were similar statistics are available.